

Distribution vs correlation trade-off in long-term correction – what is it and how to address it?

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- Introduction
- Method
- Results
- Conclusion

Intro

- In long-term correction, we are trying to find a mapping f from *reanalysis model space* til *mast data space*

Reanalysis model data

cds.climate.copernicus.eu/

Mast data

wikipedia.org/wiki/Measurement_tower

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- In long-term correction, we are trying to find a mapping f from *reanalysis model space* til *mast data space* - which we can then use to extrapolate backwards in time
- We want a result that has *high correlation* and *captures the marginal distribution well*

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Intro

Correlation

Capturing marginal distribution

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Strong correlation means that the model gives a good estimate of what the wind speed/dir would have been at a given time t

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Distribution vs correlation trade-off in LTC – what is it and how to address it?

Intro

Intro

Trade-off

It would *seem* that there is a trade-off between good correlation and capturing the marginal distribution

Two kinds of model

1. Models which try to capture both, potentially adding empirical residuals back in
2. Models which split the problem into *predictable* and *unpredictable* variability

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2. Models which split the problem into *predictable* and *unpredictable* variability

Predictable variability

- The reanalysis model captures the general trend
- Described by the **smooth function**

Unpredictable variability

- The reanalysis model with its large grid size (era5: 30km) cannot take into account local weather patterns, and structures such as buildings or trees
- Described by **confidence intervals**

Method

In a nutshell

Establish a *distribution* $p(x | t)$ for each timestep t , and:

- Use the expected value as prediction if interested in *correlation*
- Sample from $p(x | t)$ for all timesteps if interested in *marginal distribution*

Method

Quantile regression

Fitting a statistical model using an *asymmetric* loss:

$$L_p(y, f) = \begin{cases} p |y - f| & \text{if } f \leq y \\ (1 - p) |y - f(x)| & \text{if } f > y \end{cases}$$

If, for example, $p = 0.1$, you penalise overestimation *9 times harder* than underestimation. The model still wants to minimise $|y - f|$, but if it cannot bring it all the way to zero, then it will rather under- than overestimate – *9 times rather*.

The result is model which *overestimates* 10 % of the time and *underestimates* 90 % of the time, i.e. a 0.1 quantile model.

Method

In a nutshell

Establish a distribution $p(x | t)$ for each timestep t , and:

- Use the expected value as prediction if interested in *correlation*
- Sample from $p(x | t)$ for all timesteps if interested in *marginal distribution: using inverse CDF*

Results

Masts

- 4 years consecutive data (1 train, 3 test)
- Positive data quality flags

country	complexity	location	reanalysis_model_service_id	mast_height_in_m
Germany	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Denmark	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Sweden	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Brazil	Flat	On shore	siEmdBrazil	101.0
Poland	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Denmark	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Denmark	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	102.0
Denmark	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	94.0
Germany	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	106.6
The Netherlands	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	140.0
Germany	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	98.0
Germany	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Germany	Flat	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	110.0
France	Hilly	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
France	Hilly	On shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
The Netherlands	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	92.0
Germany	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0
Germany	Flat	Off shore	siemdeurope_era5	100.0

Results

Measures

- Correlation
- Earth-movers distance (EMD)

Results

Wind speed: correlation

- The XGB model finds a smoother fit than other WindPRO implemented models which improves *correlation* across the board

Results

Wind speed: distribution

- The smooth fit of XGB makes for the worst ability to capture the distribution
- XGB Quantile-Regression Sampling performs the best at capturing the distribution

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Wind direction: correlation

- Again, the smooth fit of XGB outperforms other models in terms of correlation, though not by much

Results

Wind direction: distribution

- More ambiguous results, although overall favorable

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- More ambiguous results, although overall favorable

Challenges

- When the era5 signal is *very* far from the mast signal, it is difficult to make a good prediction, but also *difficult to good estimates of the unpredictable variability*
- This point is emphasised in the case of wind *direction*, as it is harder for era5 to predict it

Generating realistic time-series

- Time series: simulations of energy trading when coupled with energy price timeseries, realistic simulations of curtailment
- To get a sample, draw from the $p(x | t)$ for each timestep

Time series

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Time series

Power spectrum

Generating realistic time-series

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- To get a sample, draw from the $p(x | t)$ for each timestep
- Compute empirical autocorrelation and encode when sampling from a *multivariate gaussian*

Covariance

Time series

Power spectrum

Conclusions

- Modelling predictable and unpredictable variability as two separate tasks is a principled way of getting the best of both worlds
- Works great for wind speed, and on par with current methods/ better for wind direction
- Solid framework for generating realistic time series

**Thank you for your
attention**

Questions?